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IN 2 WOOD

Joint Action Plan

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**FOREST CLUSTERS DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION
MEASURES OF A 6-REGION STRATEGIC JOINT ACTION PLAN
FOR KNOWLEDGE-BASED REGIONAL INNOVATION**

JOINT ACTION PLAN

D3.5

INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FÜR WALD UND HOLZ NRW e.V.

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HOLZCLUSTER STEIERMARK GMBH

ZELTWEG, AUSTRIA

TIS - TECHNO INNOVATION SÜDTIROL ALTO ADIGE KAG

BOZEN, ITALY

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IN2WOOD Joint Action Plan

Executive Summary

Forests not only preserve diverse landscapes and ecosystems, they also represent the backbone of *the forest-based sector*, embracing all industries and production chains based on and interlinked by a common resource, the natural raw material wood. Being just recently recognised as a vital source of sustainable production and employment, the sector represents a major pillar of national economies, comparable in size to other large producing sectors.

Marked by its predominantly small and micro enterprise structure and weakly developed cross-sectoral organization, it however lags considerably behind other sectors in terms of coordinated R&D and innovation efforts. *Clusters*, understood as joint efforts of businesses, authorities and science to improve inter-industry communication and collaboration, offer a new perspective for forest regions to raise their innovative capacity and competitive potential.

IN2WOOD is a joint coordination action of the *Regions of Knowledge initiative* (RoK) funded from 2010 to 2012 under the 7th Framework Programme of the European Commission. It is a partnership of six European forest regions, namely Styria (Austria), North-Rhine Westphalia (Germany), South Tyrol (Italy), Grisons (Switzerland), Banská Bystrica (Slovakia) and Carpathia (Ukraine), which aim via the elaboration of a *Joint Action Plan* (JAP) at developing a lasting network of competitive regional forest clusters and trigger new collaborations for the future strengthening of their complementary R&D potentials.

The project targets key domains in the forest sector's future development: *wood production, wood construction, wood biomass and energy, logistics, cluster development and innovation*. In a coordinated effort, the consortium analysed each region's R&D SWOT profile, compiled sets of recommended actions for each region and evaluated these reciprocally. Finally, the *Joint Actions & Strategies* were concluded, which summarize the regions' matching R&D demand and offer, strategic priorities and mutual interests as well as constellations of possible multilateral partnerships for future action and joint coordination.

Notable outstanding findings of *IN2WOOD*'s strategy phase include:

- *Forest-based cluster organizations* integrating stakeholders from forestry, wood processing and manufacturing as well as their role in regional innovation have sparked large interest among *IN2WOOD*'s partners and turn out to be a core field of future R&D activities.
- *Modern wood construction* is a cornerstone of the strategies, because it unites all positive traits of the renewable raw material, a regional value added chain and a sound use of energy within one product of excellent quality destined for people's sustainable living.
- *IN2WOOD's mentoring approach* proves to be very successful for establishing new interfaces with a large number of associated forest regions across Eastern Europe, which considerably widens the impact of the project.

The JAP lays the foundation for new R&D collaborations among complementary partner regions. The upcoming steps are dedicated to *Pilot Concepts*, which will deliver synergetic plans and proposals for follow-up projects and measures towards their implementation. These efforts will be accompanied by further *Dissemination* activities to communicate the project's purpose widely within and beyond the forest sector and obtain regional decision-makers' and stakeholders' endorsement of the foreseen actions.

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IN2WOOD's R&D OUTLOOK

Future Challenges of Europe's Forest Sector

Figure 1 - The forest sector: a cluster of value added chains based on wood

The forest sector comprises all industries with major parts of production depending on the resource wood and therewith to the forest. Unified by one common resource or commodity wood, this peculiar sector embraces a number of deeply developed value added chains that are principally based on solid wood, cellulose or energy, and which span from primary production in forestry along various stages of manufacturing to numerous, sophisticated end products for the consumer. Last but not least, the forest sector is not only about wood, but incorporates as well multiple non-wood-forest-products and services of forests. This understanding of the forest sector is actually that of a complex industrial cluster.

Strengths

- Natural resource, multiple ecosystem functions
- Wood, a raw material with excellent properties, multiple end uses, long value added chains, highly innovative fields, strong future growth
- Rooted in the regions: value added, employment, mainly SMEs, important in rural areas
- Crucial role in climate change mitigation, positive ecological footprint

Weaknesses

- Economic force perceived as insignificant in the public
- Image problems, lack of knowledge of positive features
- Structural deficits of small or micro enterprises
- Fragmentation, weak cross-sectoral organization and political support

→ The sector's strengths and weaknesses depict the decisive opportunities for sustainable development of forest regions, yet put forward the challenge of stronger cooperation.

The forest sector's economic and innovative position¹

A major employer in national economies

Europe's forest-based industries represent an unexpectedly large sector having a considerable impact on national and regional economies:

- The total EU forest sector accounts for around 5.4 million employees. The core segments wood, paper and furniture (excluding printing and publishing) account for a total 3.5 million employees.
- The EU forest sector thus represents a 3.3% share of total employment or a 15% share of the producing industries (NACE C-F). At the state level this share varies between Germany 11% and Latvia 34%. At the sub-national or regional level variances are even higher.
- Owing to a fragmented view in statistics, the forest sector's major weight is largely underestimated and also weakly recognized in economic policy.

Backlog in innovation

However, the forest-based industries are lagging far behind in terms of focused investments in R&D, which can be illustrated by the number of personnel working explicitly in R&D (see Figure 2):

- The total R&D personnel in the forest-based industries (wood, paper, furniture) account for only 10.400 employees or 1.2% of the total R&D personnel in manufacturing industries.
- Compared to other sectors (e.g. electrical/electronics, chemical and petro-based products or automobiles) and its share in manufacturing (11%), the sector stands on a decisively disadvantaged position.

Figure 2
Sectoral share of employees and R&D personnel in total manufacturing in the EU, 2007

→ The forest sector's status quo portrays the economic importance of forest-based regions in line with an urgent need for more clustering and coordination of R&D efforts !

¹ Kies 2011, based on EUROSTAT data for 2007

Clusters in European Forest Regions?

Diversity of forest regions

The forest-based sector is deeply embedded within the European regions: Manifold eco-climatic and geomorphologic conditions have led to a magnificent diversity in forest landscapes and ecosystems. The ample richness of people's traditional and modern uses of forests and wood have manifested in the development of distinct regional forest sectors or *forest regions*, each owning a specific knowledge, culture and identity in that domain.

The key question is how this regionally diverse knowledge and competence can be best maintained, nurtured and channeled for the benefit of the forest sector's future development.

Clusters, a vague concept en vogue

Clusters are understood as geographical concentrations of interrelated industries, which originated through locational competitive advantage as well as strong political impetus. The role of clusters in boosting innovation in globalized markets is the focal topic in economic research and policy. *Cluster organisations*, which are joint attempts of businesses, authorities and science to improve inter-industry communication and collaboration on the regional level, are emerging rapidly in all sectors of economy.

A new approach for a traditional sector

Clusters offer a new perspective and opportunity for forest regions to raise their innovative capacity and competitive potential.

However, the forest sector is just recently being recognised as a vital source of sustainable production for regional economies; hence the notion of *forest or wood-based clusters* is still fairly new. Among the numerous initiatives emerging across Europe in various stages of development, several successful wood cluster organisations demonstrate a significant impact on regional competitiveness.

The SME question in innovation

Innovative entrepreneurs in the forest, wood and paper chain imagine and develop astonishing products and services, often joining the old and the new, and giving the traditional material wood its place in modern society. Innovations originate in small and medium business environments with favourable, yet limited conditions for creativity. In fact, wood-based businesses are mostly family-owned, often with a traditional handicraft background and a typical small to micro scale structure (average 2-5 employees!)

Main challenges of forest clusters

Critical success factors for regional forest cluster organizations are to:

- *Find working solutions for effective cooperation of SMEs:* enterprises need to see their benefits, know their duties and build-up trust.
- *Find means and incentives to trigger innovation in SMEs:* adapted, functioning support mechanisms and instruments are urgently needed.
- *Link up more closely with the science world:* clusters are apt to translate research findings into a commonly understandable language for business.
- *Trickle down of R&D results:* within the forest-based sector, intermediaries play a key role to facilitate and improve trickle down effects by bridging the gap between research and business and by organizing pre-competitive R&D
- *Increase interaction among regional forest clusters:* explore the potentials of interregional knowledge exchange, mutual learning and cooperation.

IN2WOOD's Strategic Coordination

Project Key Facts

IN2WOOD is a joint coordination action carried out by a partnership of six European forest regions committed to develop a lasting network of competitive regional forest clusters (see Figure 3). The overall goal is to improve the trans-national integration of regional research agendas through the elaboration of a Joint Action Plan (JAP) for the future coordination and strengthening of their complementary RTD potentials.

- Title** IN2WOOD - Forest Clusters Development and Implementation Measures of a 6-Region Strategic Joint Action Plan for Knowledge-based Regional Innovation
- Framework** FP7 Capacities, Regions of Knowledge (RoK), 2009-1
- Lifetime** 2010/01 – 2012/06 (30 months)
- Budget** EC contribution: 2.3 Mio. €
- Partners** 6 regions: Styria, Austria; North-Rhine Westphalia, Germany; South Tyrol, Italy; Grisons, Switzerland; Banská Bystrica, Slovakia; Carpathia, Ukraine.
13 organizations in *triple helix clusters* (business + regional authority + science)

Figure 3 - IN2WOOD's Regions of Knowledge Network Map

General Objectives

IN2WOOD deals with the challenges of sustainable European forest management and the R&D environment of the forest-based sector (see Figure 4). The project aims at five key domains in the sector's future development (GO = General Objectives):

- GO.1 Wood Production** → In the field of *forestry*, which represents the initial link of wood-based value added chains, the focus is to explore forest management systems designed adaptive to climate change, surging wood markets and a rising demand for the raw material wood.
- GO.3 Competence Awareness** → In *wood construction* and *biomass and energy*, which represent important and highly dynamic branches in the forest sector, wood and its multiple uses as a modern (urban) construction material and energy source are enhanced and promoted.
- GO.4 Logistics** → The *logistics'* interconnections and processes between the forest sector's branches are enhanced regarding new technologies, optimized workflows and supply chain management.
- GO.2, GO.5 Innovation & Information Systems** → IN2WOOD puts a special focus on developing the role of *regional clusters* in the forest sector, namely their organizational know-how and tools in information services and innovation support management.

Figure 4 - IN2WOOD in a nutshell: partner regions, major strategic fields, project phases

Steps of the Strategy Process

IN2WOOD targets the potentials of the research-driven regional forest clusters to lever future opportunities for RTD collaboration. The joint strategy development process followed a stepwise logic of separate work packages (see Figure 4):

- WP.1**
PM
- The project management established and ensured the overall coordination and communication of the consortium, the administrative organization, the fulfillment of the DoW requirements and reporting on the deliverables.
- WP.2**
Analyses
- The initial step (months 1-7) aimed at a *substantial analysis of the state of play* of the research-driven clusters in the six regions. It identified strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in the state of knowledge and targeted the regions' potentials and priorities of complementary R&D needs.
- > *Outcome*: Six regional analyses interim reports D2.1-D2.5
- WP.3**
Strategies
- In the second step (months 8-18), the WP.2 cross-regional matching of topics was refined and strategic activities were drafted. Based on a reciprocal evaluation of regionally specific R&D priorities (see next chapter), the collection concludes a *coordinated set of future joint strategies and actions*.
- > *Outcome*: Six regional strategy reports D3.1-D3.5, the JAP D3.6 (this report)
- WP.4**
Pilot
Concepts
- Measures towards the implementation of the JAP are taken in phase II (months 19-30) in the form of pilot concepts, which are *synergetic project ideas* defining complementary partnerships, plans and funding schemes for innovative follow-up projects.
- > *Outcome*: A number of concrete new projects have already been initiated or are under preparation. See chapter 'Pilot Concepts'.
- WP.5**
Mentoring
- Fostering knowledge exchange and cluster formation, IN2WOOD's mentoring interface *strengthens relationships among stakeholders* within and between the partner regions and initiates networking with new associated forest regions, especially in (South-) Eastern Europe (see map figure 3).
- > *Outcome*: The IN2WOOD Cluster Cooperation Network currently comprises new contacts to circa 50 institutions of 11 countries in (South-) Eastern Europe. See chapter 'Mentoring' and report D5.3.
- WP.6**
Dissemination
- To communicate the forest sector's key strength and opportunities for sustainable development to a range of decision-makers in industry and policy, the project's outcomes are disseminated via *events, platforms and publications* pointing at a wider public in and beyond the forest sector.
- > *Outcome*: A number of major events, notably the IN2WOOD conference at the LIGNA Fair in Hannover, and various smaller activities have been realized. See chapter 'Dissemination' and report D6.3.

JOINT STRATEGIES & ACTIONS

Sustainable Forestry Sustaining Europe's Green Gold for the Future

R&D Priorities

Trends, Challenges

The future of Europe's forests and forest sector is influenced by several global trends: a continuous decrease in forest area per capita and a substantial increase in demand for wood material continue to widen the gap between supply and demand and a growing competition between solid/material uses vs. energetic use vs. chemical use of wood. In addition, climate change and disastrous weather turbulences decisively alter the forests' structure, stability and productivity. These trends will inevitably lead to a relative scarcity of the raw material wood and dynamic structural shifts in the forest sector.

Strategic Goals

The IN2WOOD regions identified four major lines of common goals to take into account these key challenges and adapt their wood production and sustainable forest use to them:

- Tackling climate change with adaptive silviculture
- Unlocking sustainable wood resource potentials
- Exploring new dendromass sources and systems
- Valorising new non-wood forest products and services

Considering their mutual strengths and opportunities, the partner regions foresee to jointly develop the following set of future R&D activities.

Wood Construction

Competence Awareness in Modern Living

R&D Priorities

Trends and Challenges

Today a new generation of consumers recognises the modernity of wood, a remarkably versatile material that fits precisely into a rapidly changing civilisation scenario. The future development of Europe's wood construction sector is influenced by several global trends: while the economic significance of wood construction remains generally underestimated, wooden products face a decreasing competitiveness as time labour saving technologies are expanding rapidly and technologically advanced products are largely gaining in attractiveness. These trends will sharpen the divide between saving a balance of market forces and a growing public demand for environmental and social services of forests and lead to structural changes in wood construction.

Strategic Goals

The IN2WOOD regions identified four major categories of common strategic interest to deal with these challenges and boost the markets for wood as an energy efficient and sustainable construction material:

- Changing attitudes towards wood and abolish restriction in building codes
- Increasing market penetration in existing customer segments and tapping new market segments
- Development of products and processes increasing the competitiveness of wood as a construction material
- Instruments providing knowledge exchange, qualification and training programs to improve and harmonize existing know-how across regions and to increase the overall quality of timber constructions.

Considering their mutual strengths and opportunities, the partner regions foresee to jointly develop the following set of future R&D activities.

Wood Biomass and Energy

Competence Awareness in Renewable Energy

R&D | Priorities

Trends and Challenges

Spurred by a wide range of European directives on the use of renewables, international agreements on climate protection actions, and national biomass action plans, the utilization of biomass as an energy carrier has gained a very dynamic momentum in the past. However, this led to a previously unknown fierce competition for raw timber between material end uses and energetic uses. The concern over a shortage of raw timber was further fueled by harsh discussions between industries and environmental groups claiming a reduction of forest management activities in favor of stronger nature conservation. Given the continuously increasing demand for energy wood, strategies aiming solely at wood mobilization are not likely to fill the gap between timber supply and demand. To mitigate anticipated raw timber price hikes, forest industries are challenged to find new ways to reconcile raw material supply and demand for the whole sector without forgoing business opportunities of the various stakeholders in the wood value chain.

Strategic Goals

The IN2WOOD regions identified four major lines of common goals to develop a proper management of forest ecosystems and a sustainable supply of woody biomass as a source of renewable energy:

- Analysis of regional supply and demand for biomass
- Enhancing wood mobilization in order to increase the resource base by including primary and secondary sources
- Identify R&D demand for technological progress
- Identify and exploit new business opportunities

Considering their mutual strengths and opportunities, the partner regions foresee to jointly develop the following set of future R&D activities.

Logistics

Synergize Forces along Regional Supply Chains

R&D Priorities

Trends, Challenges

Logistics play an important role in forestry and the wood working sector. For round wood and biomass, the costs of harvesting, handling, manipulation and transport sum up to a significant percentage of the overall costs of the raw material, although considerable differences in costs exist depending on the origin of the raw material. Lowland forest regions are advantaged due to a good access to the raw material, allowing the use of heavy harvesting machinery and modern technologies such as GPS tracking to optimise the workflow, and at the same time to minimize the impact on the ecosystem, especially on soils. In mountainous regions, harvesting activities are much more cumbersome to carry out due to a number of the circumstances like steep terrain and climatic conditions. Technological progress and new business models are necessary to guarantee and enhance the competitiveness of wood logistics under these variable regional environments.

Strategic Goals

The IN2WOOD regions identified four major categories of common strategic interest to address the challenges in wood logistics:

- Elaborate reliable basic information for the forest and wood working sector regarding material flows in the region
- Interconnect the single players in the supply chain by enhancing vertical co-operations
- Increase the use of ICT within supply chain management
- Elaborate and adapt master emergency plans for storm damages to regional needs

Considering their mutual strengths and opportunities, the partner regions foresee to jointly develop the following set of future R&D activities.

Clusters and Innovation

Strengthen Competitive Forest Regions in Europe

R&D Priorities

Trends, Challenges

Clusters, competence centres and regional networks play a crucial role in boosting innovation in wood industries, yet the forest sector is still considered a “low-tech” industry, which invests comparatively little into research and development and is mainly an innovation follower. The regional cluster initiatives' future depends on their proper definition of their role as a promoter and facilitator of joint collaboration and the need to offer competitive support services to their members and clients. Involvement of private enterprises will only be successful if clear benefits and opportunities for businesses are visible. The initiative must not be *“paralysed by analyses”* (quote ClusterNavigators), but give hard results and solutions that work.

Strategic Goals

The IN2WOOD regions identified three major categories of common strategic interest to address the challenges of regional cluster organizations:

- Enhance cluster formation, facilitation and management
- Develop and promote tailored innovation support programs and services
- Build up cluster information systems and communication platforms

Considering their mutual strengths and opportunities, the partner regions foresee to jointly develop the following set of future R&D activities.

STEPS TOWARDS IMPLEMENTATION

Dissemination

Rationale The forest-based sector is strongly underrated in Europe. Across national states and regions it can be observed that economic policy and development support most often only take into account sectors believed to stand for innovation and competitiveness: the bio- nano- micro- and IT sectors.

The wood-based value added chains – even if connected with a substantial GNP and employment rate- are not recognized as drivers for a modern and sustainable “resource-oriented” economy of the future society. Here, the IN2WOOD process, based on intense international networking beyond the core partnership and across the value-added chains, sets off. Within IN2WOOD, the “mentoring” concept of ROK has experienced a profound change in the perception by the consortium: what was an obligatory task and difficult to manage is now feeding the core message of the project.

The focus towards South-Eastern Europe allowed integrating within a short time closely interrelated partners into the IN2WOOD network. The message becomes visible in a convincing way: to open up, exchange knowledge and cooperate across borders in Europe and to improve the competence awareness for the innovation and sustainable economic potential of the European forest-based sector.

- Objectives**
- Form a politically anchored alliance to support the European collaboration of regional wood and forest-based clusters
 - Join regional authorities (e.g. state forest administrations) for a mutual consultation process on sustainable forest management
 - Improve the acceptance and awareness of the wood and forest-based economy within the regional and European strategy development

Benefits for IN2WOOD partners The partners already benefit from the awareness created by the IN2WOOD dissemination activities. The close interrelation of the mentoring and the dissemination process developed successfully as was demonstrated during five days of IN2WOOD activities at the LIGNA Fair 2011 in Hannover, including an exhibition booth, the IN2WOOD Conference and the IN2WOOD Cooperation Workshop. Based on the aim to establish a living network, high-level meetings of experts have already resulted in gains of self-confidence and acceptance within the regional opinion leaders/ authority circles. Significant activities towards more internationalization have been set up, leading to more interaction on consortium level (-> event planned in Styria for Oct 2011 joining IN2WOOD, RokFor and Bioclus), on a political level (-> visit of NRW’s Minister for Environment and Agriculture in Styria planned for Sep 2011) and on a expert level (-> education program / technology transfer / market development in wood construction, afforestation of wastelands and coal mining areas, woody biomass logistics, forest-based ecotourism).

Current Progress and Outcomes

- Interrelation of the mentoring and the dissemination process created a visible network of 17 European forest regions
- Involving the regional triple helix in most of the regions guarantees for fast dissemination along personal interconnections and relationships
- Competence awareness of the forest-based sector has been improved within the regional stakeholder networks/authorities by internationalization
- Interaction “beyond” the forest sector (chemical industry, logistics and building sector) is supported by the “corporate identity” of IN2WOOD

Upcoming Steps

- Public version of the JAP
- Publication of regional versions of WP.3 Strategy Reports and JAP
- Other publications (working titles):
 - “Logistics Strategies in 6 Regions”
 - “Impacts of Climate Change on Host - Parasite Interaction in Present and Future Forests”
 - “Germany - Slovakia - Serbia: possibilities for reclaiming of Kolubara mining area”

- Regional events related to the pilot concept development
- Study tours & networking activities
- Presentations of IN2WOOD at other events
- Forthcoming IN2WOOD events:

Oct 2011: IN2WOOD workshop in Styria on woody biomass joining RokFor, Bioclus and IN2WOOD experts

Nov 2011: “Urban Wood” workshop in North Rhine-Westphalia, Ruhr Area, joining building and housing industry, timber construction experts from Styria, Switzerland, South Tyrol, Bulgaria and NRW

Jan 2012: Deubau, international trade fair for construction – IN2WOOD presentation within the common booth of the LBWuH

April/May 2012: IN2WOOD final conference, high Tatras, combined with the annual Forestry Event “Actual problems in the Forest”

May/June 2012: IN2WOOD final event in Brussels, with invited ministers from NRW and a mentoring partner region; supported by the state representations of the IN2WOOD partners in Brussels.

Mentoring

Rationale	Europe's forest regions are rather weakly interconnected and new knowledge spreads rather arbitrarily. Here the European R&D support programmes offer decisive opportunities for the regions to unlock the forest sector's potentials in sustainable development. Through its mentoring process, IN2WOOD opens up new channels for knowledge exchange, mutual learning and innovative interregional thinking that strengthens the clusters within their regions and contributes to the sector's position within Europe's future knowledge society.
Objective	Within IN2WOOD, mentoring is understood as a systematic communication process to build up personal networks and compatible partnerships for mutual learning and lasting future collaboration among forest regions and forest sector institutions in (South-)Eastern Europe.
Why South-Eastern Europe as target region?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The European Union works towards a stronger integration of the new member states and neighbours. ▪ (South-)Eastern Europe holds large, less developed forest resources with a comparatively average lower land use pressure than in Western Europe. At the same time, the wood-based industries are very dynamic as they are emerging anew in the context of post-socialist economies. ▪ The region is gaining in importance as a strategic market for foreign investors, with various up and downsides, e.g. new investments and employment, technological progress, relocation of production capacities, cut-throat competition, overexploitation, illegal logging. ▪ Strengthening forest-based clusters in the region is seen an important step to positively balance the complex effects of the sector's dynamics.
Targets	<p>IN2WOOD's unique mentoring process is a crosscutting project activity and builds on four steps of successful communication. Its main targets include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Involvement of a large number of stakeholders → Identification of new RTD clusters as partners for follow-up projects → Preparatory setup of a European Forest Cluster Initiative
Aims and benefits of mentoring partners	<p>Mentoring is by no means a one way approach. Based on their special experience and know-how, IN2WOOD partners may have both roles of mentor and mentee during the process. Each target mentoring region has outstanding experience and expertise, too, from which the network may learn and benefit.</p> <p><i>Networking, mobility</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enlarging and interconnecting regional experts' networks - Partnering events, study trips, business delegations, b2b matching - Databases and directories of partners competences <p><i>Sharing of knowledge, mutual learning</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge exchange on wood cluster best practice - Excellence and unique competences among partners - Experiences of emerging/embryonic clusters

Joint R&D projects

- Joint initiation, preparation and implementation
- Bilateral vs. multilateral, cross-border vs. European projects

Joint PR and marketing

- Joint, cross-regional dissemination activities
- Joint representation on fairs and trade shows

Capacity building and personnel development

- Specialised trainings, exchange programs, e.g. on cluster management
- Joint university and business school programs
- Shared special resources, e.g. network of business angels, advisors

Policy advice

- Decision-making support to regional policy and decision-makers
- Joint interest representation on regional, national and EU-Level

**Current
Progress and
Outcomes**

The mentoring process has been implemented as a horizontal project activity in a series of workshops, conferences, partnering events and bilateral communications (for further details see the documentation in report D5.3). The most notable outcomes are:

- The IN2WOOD Cluster Cooperation Network currently comprises new contacts outside the IN2WOOD consortium to approx. 50 institutions of 11 countries in Eastern Europe.
- Major events fostering partnering and exchange on new collaboration include the Klagenfurt workshop (Aug 26-28, 2010), the Olsberg meeting (Dec 7-8, 2010) and the Hannover workshop (June 1, 2011).
- Mentoring partners have become directly involved as external experts into IN2WOOD's strategy process and pilot concept development.
- IN2WOOD helped to match new bilateral partnerships between invited institutions among the mentoring regions.
- Linkages to other European projects and consortia emerged from mentoring.
- Several new European proposals of IN2WOOD partners were developed involving new partners from the mentoring process.

**Upcoming
Steps**

The mentoring process will continue and intensify for the lasting project time. Mentoring partners participate in the working groups as collaborators, contribute to the formulation of the pilot concepts and provide further dissemination events. Mentoring partner play an integral role in the project concepts and as multipliers and network nodes within their regions.

Pilot Concepts

Rationale	<p>The pilot concepts are defined as preparatory work for post-project realization: “Specified RTD input from the partnering regions shall lead to clearly focused innovative concepts including feasibility analyses and financing/funding schemes. Pilot concepts prepare joint best practice examples, which are designed to be realized by partners in a regionally well adapted way with regionally differing priorities.”</p> <p>The definition of pilot concepts needs to be extended at this point of the project: the larger IN2WOOD network including the mentoring partners will be involved into the concept development. Matching competences and needs revealed potentially successful partnerships. Ripening the collection of strategic actions and feeding them into realistic implementation planning including financing mechanisms is now the prerequisite for continuity in collaboration among IN2WOOD members and mentoring partners beyond the projects lifetime.</p>
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Benefit from IN2WOOD wider networks expertise, opportunities and needs → Define innovative concepts within a realistic frame → Use topic-related collaborations to form stable alliances and involve regional authorities, thereby supporting long-term sustainability in the European forest-based sector → Link pilot concepts and their future developments to IN2WOOD
Steps of WP.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) <i>Address and involve regional stakeholders</i> b) <i>Define technical, political and financial frameworks</i> c) <i>Identify funding mechanisms:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Compile info on funding framework ▪ Check funding opportunities for Joint Actions JAP ▪ Involve relevant stakeholders in industry and regional / national authorities d) <i>Draft pilot concepts, collect commitment, start implementation</i>
Current Progress and Outcomes	<p>First pilot concepts discussed with partners and mentoring partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Wastelands and plantation forestry of coal mining areas (NRW + Styria + Serbia + Bulgaria) ▪ Forest-based ecotourism collaboration (NRW + Carpathia) ▪ Urban wood competence (Styria + Grisons + South Tyrol + NRW) ▪ Wood biomass resource potential assessment (Banská Bystrica + NRW + mentoring partners) ▪ Regional logistical chain optimization (Styria + South Tyrol + Grisons + Banská Bystrica + Western Macedonia)

- Developing emerging new regional cluster organizations (Grisons + Carpathia + NRW)
- European Forest Metacluster Initiative (NRW + Styria + mentoring partners)

Upcoming Steps

The above mentioned list reflects an actual status of discussion and preparatory steps. It shows that the initially proposed pilot concepts have developed different emphases since their first description in the DoW.

The main task of the next months is to concentrate on the pilot concepts selection and define responsible drivers and the collaboration core group for each pilot concept. Involving relevant stakeholders (regional and national authorities, industry) into the concept development from the very beginning shall ensure that funding possibilities on different levels are screened efficiently.

Outlook beyond IN2WOOD

The outlook for progress of the IN2WOOD European wood cluster collaboration initiative after the projects lifetime depends on the capability to interlink the collaboration activities defined by the pilot concepts.

The problem of linking topics related to completely different actors and target groups relates to the core challenge of wood and forest-based clusters: they define themselves on the basis of the resource “wood” and try to meet requirements of the whole value-added chain linking the complex forest ecosystem up to heating, building, design and lingo-cellulosic composites.

Is such a resource-oriented integrative effort still feasible today - regarding our effect- and product oriented economic strategies? The “resource-oriented society” is said to be replaced gradually by a “knowledge-oriented” society. However, wood as a resource has a special status: it needs to be “grown” and managed carefully in long cycles, it involves a truly broad range of innovative usage opportunities and it keeps its qualities in all its manifold manifestations.

Even while facing the difficulties of dealing with very different stakeholders such as forest owners, foresters, wood industry managers, energy plant operators, architects, designers etc., the forest and wood-based clusters stick to a resource-oriented innovation strategy, strongly rooted in the regions.

IN2WOOD challenge is that of all wood and forest clusters: if several of the proposed “pilot concepts” can be successfully developed and supported by additionally acquired funding, this will provide a set of nuclei stabilizing further collaboration of the network. The question remains whether it is still manageable to feed those posterior activities into a joint platform.

Successful transfer of the “pilot concepts” into “pilot projects” has to be accompanied by interlinking and extending the IN2WOOD network not only by stable working relationships, but also by maintaining and further developing a “corporate identity” and working structures for a visible European network of regional forest and wood-based clusters.

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